

STUDENTS' DEVELOPMENT OF LEXICAL SKILLS THROUGHOUT ENGLISH SESSIONS

Tadjimova Shaxnoza Rashidovna

Assistant-teacher

Tashkent University of Information Technology, Nukus branch

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11118347>

Acquiring proficiency in a foreign language has long since transcended its status as a trendy pastime and is now considered a vital necessity. A young specialist needs to be able to speak at least one foreign language in order to advance in their job. Our main goal is to teach the student to fully and competently express his point of view on a given problem because the Federal State Educational Standard requires that after mastering the foreign language discipline, the student must be able to communicate (orally and in writing) in a foreign language on topics related to daily life and the workplace. Furthermore, a person needs a large vocabulary in order for the statement to be complete and for them to have no trouble selecting words or putting phrases together. The degree to which a student successfully masters the lexical structure of a foreign language depends on the teacher's pedagogical skill.

What is vocabulary? S.I. Ozhegova's explanatory dictionary defines vocabulary as a language's vocabulary, which is made up of a collection of words and associations that act similarly to one another to build a certain system. "Vocabulary" is defined in the foreign language teaching technique as the vocabulary (passive and active) that the student possesses or ought to possess. To master this discipline, a student must acquire a certain amount of lexical units, which are determined by the Federal State Educational Standard.

There are several explanations for why language learning has become more important: The level of lexical competency determines the substance of the utterance. There are differences in the psychological and psycholinguistic properties of the vocabulary that needs to be taught.

The lexical minimum that has been learnt ought to be regarded as fundamental (reference) vocabulary.

Speaking, reading, and listening are examples of speech tasks that depend on proficiency with language units.

The intricate process of learning vocabulary in a foreign language can be broken down into multiple phases from a methodological perspective:

1. introduction of fresh lexical units,
2. Semantization (revealing the meaning of newly created,
3. command of the new vocabulary comprehension
4. picking up new vocabulary and idioms and memorizing them
5. instruction on how to perceive and use new vocabulary.

Depending on the teaching strategy employed in the classroom, students' work on the development of lexical abilities at a given stage will vary. According to the contemporary communicative approach to teaching foreign languages, new LE ought to be presented in contexts that reflect authentic communication and are relevant to this age group's interests. A few years ago, the traditional approach to teaching foreign languages suggested exercises like reading aloud and memorization of vocabulary, but today, this approach is seen as

inappropriate and goes against the purpose of teaching a foreign language, which is to "achieve a minimum sufficient level of communicative competence" or practically master the language.

There are a variety of exercises to practice vocabulary in order to solidify it. The three guiding concepts of vocabulary instruction are student independence, situationality, and systematicity. Exercises should mimic authentic communication scenarios, be engaging, varied, and help students improve their language skills.

There is constant and intentional work done to expand student's vocabulary. It's no secret that there is a dearth of specialist literature for foreign language instructors. Furthermore, it is nearly impossible to locate textbooks in the specialization for the departments of Construction and Operation of Buildings and Structures and Design, Modeling, and Technology of Sewing Products if the selection of textbooks for the computer department is sufficiently broad. Lexical notebooks, which include unique texts and multi-level sets of exercises for introducing, consolidating, and training lexical material, have been designed specifically for students studying in these fields. The phases of vocabulary development for students can be seen clearly in these tasks.

To sum up, it is important to stress once more how a lack of vocabulary makes students feel uneasy and discourages them from speaking a foreign language. For this reason, the teacher's primary goal in the classroom should be to help students grow their active vocabulary and develop their ability to communicate on their own.

References:

1. Gez N.I. Methods of teaching foreign languages in secondary school. – M.: Higher. school, 1982. – 373 p.
2. Kozhevnikov, D.N. Using Game Design and Simulation for Development cognitive abilities of children / D.N. Kozhevnikov // Primary education. – 2011. – No. 6. - WITH.36-43.
3. Konysheva A.V. Game method in teaching a foreign language / A.V. Konysheva. – SPb.: KARO, Mn.: Publishing house "Four Quarters", 2006. – 192 p.
4. Leontyev A.A. Language and speech activity in general and pedagogical psychology / A.A. Leontyev. – M: RAO/MPSI, 2001. – 127 p.